

JOB ANXIETY AND BURNOUT AMONG THE HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS OF TENKASI EDUCATIONAL DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The study examined that the job anxiety and burnout among the high school teachers of Tenkasi educational district in relation to the background variables. A self-made scale was used to measure the job anxiety of 154 high school teachers from Tenkasi District, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. A simple random sampling method was adopted for analyzing the data and framed the suitable null hypotheses. The result showed that job anxiety and burnout among the high school teachers of Tenkasi educational District is significant.

Key Words: Job Anxiety, Burnout & High School Teachers

Introduction:

The word 'education' has a very wide meaning. It is as old as the human race. It is a never ending process of inner growth and development and its period stretches from cradle to grave. It is very important for the progress of individual and society. It is through education that man develops his thinking and reasoning, problem solving and creativity, skills, values, attitudes and intelligence etc. In fact, man's entire life is education. Ever since the dawn of civilization, man directly or indirectly has been trying to educate himself in order to meet with the changing demands of life. In fact, he has succeeded in distinguishing himself from other animals only by virtue of education. During the course of time, education became an essential virtue for man to live and lead a civilized life. It has humanizing role. Man becomes a human being when he goes through the process of education.

Education is an integral part of human life. It is the basic condition for the development of the whole world and vital instrument accelerating the well-being and the prosperity of all in every direction. Without education, man would still believing just like a splendid slave or live seasoning savage. It is a tool which helps to develop the human behaviour. It is a process of human enlightenment and empowerment for the achievement of a better and higher quality of life. The purpose of education is to improve the cognitive ability, habits, skills and attitudes in order to lead a full and worthwhile life in this world. Educated people can find out what they need to know. Educated people share a common body of knowledge with other educated people that aid them in finding out what they need to know.

Significance of the Study:

The status of any profession is determined in large measures by the quality of the professional service which depends on the adequacy of the insights and understandings on which professional decisions are based. Teachers can improve their professional skill with, which they guide students growth and development only if they have a thorough understanding of the principles of the psychology. "Teachers are primarily responsible for students' achievement" (Anandharaja, Balakrishnan, Lawrence, 2016). "National development depends on the quality of teachers" (Maju & Asha, 2016) and so their responsibility is great. Emotionally matured teachers tackle problems which may arise in teaching –learning evaluation of pupils' progress, classroom management and discipline as well as the problem of human relationship both within the school and outside the school and community. Teachers' anxiety will definitely have an effect on the classroom situation and it is a central factor in facilitating or retarding pupil learning and it also constitute a factor in providing job satisfaction to the teacher. The understanding of the role of teacher's anxiety in teaching and learning has now led to the generation of much interest in creating a favorable classroom environment and school climate. It is also playing the role in deciding teacher's anxiety.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of job anxiety among the high school teachers.
- ✓ To find out the level of job anxiety among the high school teachers with regard to gender.
- ✓ To find out the level of burnout among the high school teachers.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between job anxiety and burnout of high school teachers with reference to gender.
- ✓ To find out the significant relationship between job anxiety and burnout schoolteachers.

Null Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in job anxiety among the high school teachers with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in burnout among the high school teachers with regard to gender.

- ✓ There is no significant relationship between job anxiety and burnout among high school teachers.

Methodology:

The researcher has used to the survey method for obtaining the data.

Sample for the Study:

The investigator has randomly selected 154 high school teachers from Tenkasi Educational Districts.

Tool Used:

- ✓ The researcher has used the standardized scale for job anxiety Priya and Antony Sagaya Ruban (2017).
- ✓ Questionnaire for measuring burnout – prepared and validated by Maslach’s burnout inventory (1986).

Statistical Techniques Used:

Percentage analysis, Arithmetic mean, Standard deviation, ‘t’ test, ANOVA, Chi-Square test, Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation were used for analysis of the data.

Descriptive Analysis and Results:

Table 1: Level of Job Anxiety of High School Teachers with Regard to Total Sample

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Job Anxiety	28	18.2	99	64.3	27	17.5

It is inferred from the above table shows that 18.2% of low level, 64.3% of moderate level and 17.5% of high level of Job Anxiety.

Table 2: Level of job anxiety of high school teachers with regard to gender

Variables	Category	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender	Male	17	23.6	45	62.5	10	13.9
	Female	11	13.4	54	65.9	17	20.7

It is inferred from the above table shows that 23.6 % of male high school teachers have low level, 62.5 % of them have moderate and 13.9 % of them have high level of job anxiety.

It is inferred from the above table shows that 13.4% of female high schools teachers have low level, 65.9% of them have moderate and 20.7% of them have high level of job anxiety.

Table 3: Level of Burnout of High School Teachers with Regard to Total Sample

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Burnout	28	12.3	99	75.3	27	12.3

It is inferred from the above table shows that 12.3% of low level, 75.3% of moderate level and 12.3% of high level of Burnout.

Table 4: Level of burnout of high school teachers with regard to gender

Variable	Category	Low		Moderate		high	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender	Male	13	18.1	50	69.4	9	12.5
	Female	6	7.3	66	80.5	10	12.2

It is inferred from the above table shows that 18.1 % of male high schools teachers have low level, 69.4 % of them have moderate and 12.5 % of them have high level of burnout.

It is inferred from the above table shows that 7.3% of female high schools teachers have low level, 80.5% of them have moderate and 12.2% of them have high level of burnout.

Hypotheses Testing:

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in job anxiety among the high school teachers with regard to gender.

Table 5: Difference between male and female high school teachers in their job anxiety

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ value	Remark
Gender	Male	72	50.07	7.330	0.783	NS
	Female	82	50.98	6.969		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of ‘t’ is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table shows that there is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their job anxiety.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in burnout among the high school teachers with regard to gender.

Table 6: Difference between male and female high school teachers in their burnout

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ value	Remark
Gender	Male	57	32.95	3.943	0.422	NS
	Female	97	32.65	4.670		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table shows that there is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their burnout.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the Job Anxiety and Burnout of High School Teachers.

Table 7: Relationship between the Job Anxiety And Burnout of High School Teachers

ΣX	ΣY	ΣX^2	ΣY^2	ΣXY	N	γ Value	Table Value	Remark
7785	5045	401327	168241	257507	154	0.515	0.117	S

It is inferred from the above table shows that shows that there is significant relationship between Job anxiety and Burnout of high School Teachers.

Findings based on Descriptive Analysis:

- ✓ 17.5% of high school teachers have high level of job anxiety.
- ✓ 13.9% of male and 20.7% of female teachers have high level of job anxiety.
- ✓ 12.3% of high school teachers have high level of burnout.
- ✓ 12.5% of male and 12.2% of female teachers have high level of burnout.

Findings based on Hypotheses Testing:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their job anxiety.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between male and female high school teachers in their burnout.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Job anxiety and Burnout of high School Teachers.

Implications:

- ✓ To create a healthy climate self-awareness program should be arranged for teachers.
- ✓ There should be a cordial relationship between teachers and the head of the institution.
- ✓ The teachers at secondary level should also be given one or two leisure periods keeping in mind of their work load.
- ✓ The head of the institution should provide the opportunity for suitable working space, facilities to achieve one's status and prestige in job etc.

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